

RULES FOR ORGANIZING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN A SOCIAL STATE

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Abstract. *This article provides a scientific and philosophical analysis of the rules for organizing inclusive education in a social state.*

Keywords: *social state, inclusive, continuing education, individual, rule, ability.*

In most developed countries of the world, there are standards and principles aimed at making the educational environment equal, comfortable and effective for all children, including students with disabilities or developmental differences, which can be seen in the following. The rules of inclusive education: Every person has the ability to think and feel. Everyone has the ability to hear and communicate. Everyone needs each other. A person's full and true education can only be achieved in real partnership. Everyone needs the support of their peers. The success of all learners is determined not by what they cannot do, but by what they can do. In classes in general education schools implementing inclusive education, the number of integrated students does not exceed 2-3 people, and the total number of students is set at 25 people.

At the same time, in a rapidly developing society, it is important to educate children with disabilities, develop educational programs aimed at them, and develop measures to direct them to a profession based on their needs. This is the reason for the increasing need for inclusive education today.

Needs for inclusive education: Every person has needs for love, trust, protection, encouragement of personal activity, and so on. Disabled people are no exception, but in addition to these, they have their own individual needs. Even if their disabilities are similar, based on their behavior, interests, abilities, etc., they are different from each other. Every child is a unique individual and needs help to adapt to life and develop. Children with disabilities can also engage in joint activities with healthy children. Children with disabilities also have the right to study and be educated alongside their healthy peers. The following can be achieved as a result of involving children with disabilities in education:

As a result,

- inclusive education will allow children with disabilities to always be in the circle of their family neighborhood and relatives;
- improve the regulatory and legal framework;
- form a friendly attitude towards children with disabilities;
- start corrective measures from an early age that will allow achieving positive results in the development of the child;
- organize medical-psychological-pedagogical monitoring, that is, constant assistance from specialists, for each child involved in general education;
- ensure the necessary forms of upbringing and education of each child with disabilities together with healthy children.
- inclusive education can serve as a catalyst for improving the quality of education for all;
- early integration into society, equal rights with their peers.
- ensuring that all children understand that they are children like them and do not discriminate against people with disabilities.

There are a number of difficulties in providing education to children with disabilities, which creates various obstacles to the effective implementation of the activities of educational institutions and teachers organizing inclusive education. In particular, the following problems of inclusive education can be listed:

- lack of provision of educational and methodological literature;
- negative attitude towards children with disabilities;
- invisibility of children with disabilities among their healthy peers;
- lack of adaptation of educational institutions;
- large number of students in the classroom;
- dependence of children with disabilities on others;
- problems with personnel issues.
- lack of understanding of society and parents about the essence of inclusive education.

As a result of analyzing and classifying these difficulties, we identify the aspects necessary for the development of inclusive education:

In a social state, the formation of correct understandings of racism, disability, and the breadth of opportunities in the minds of children is of great importance in increasing the effectiveness of inclusive education. Due to the existence of incorrect understandings, children with disabilities are exposed to insults and ridicule. What is even more tragic is that some educators ignore such negative attitudes. To increase the effectiveness of education, it is necessary to create an equal, loving, friendly and warm environment for all children in all schools.

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